

INDIGOID VAT DYES OF THE ISATIN SERIES. PART V. 3-INDOLE
2'-(5'-CHLORO) THIONAPHTHENE-INDIGOS

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A few 3-indole-2'-(5'-chloro)thionaphthene-indigos have been prepared by condensing 5-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene with isatin and some of its substituted products respectively. Their colour and the dyeing shades on wool and on cloth have been compared with those obtained from the mother compounds as well as from the corresponding 5'-methyl compounds.

5 : 5'-Dichloro-thioindigo has been obtained in violet-red needle-shaped crystals.

The studies on the influence of a methyl radical, when present in every theoretically possible different position of the thionaphthene nucleus of 3-indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigos, were made complete in previous parts of this series of papers as the result of which a relation between the change in colour and constitution of a good number of isomeric 3-indole-2'-(methyl)thionaphthene-indigos was deduced (Guha and Basu-Mallick, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 395 ; Guha, *ibid.*, 1937, 14, 240 ; 1938, 15, 501 ; 1944, 21, 87).

With a view to testing how far this holds good in the case of 3-indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigos having a different type of substituent present in the thionaphthene ring of the molecule of the dyes, the present investigation was undertaken. Here the substituent chosen is Cl atom which is not the same in character as the methyl radical.

5-Chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (D.R.P. 224567 ; Friedländer, *Ber.*, 1877, 10, 474 ; Auwers and Thies, *Ber.*, 1920, 53, 2285) has been condensed with isatin and its 5-bromo-5 : 7-dibromo, and 5 : 7-dinitro derivatives respectively and another series of thioindigoid dyes prepared which may be represented by the general formula (I).

These 5'-chloro compounds are violet-red crystalline substances ; all are soluble in pyridine and nitrobenzene, sparingly soluble in alcohol. Cold concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves them producing either faint or deep blue solution from which the original dyes are re-precipitated unchanged in a flocculent state on the addition of water. They melt when heated above 290°. They easily impart deep shades to cloth from alkaline hydro-sulphite vat and the dyeing shades on wool have been also uniformly developed from an acid bath.

The various isomeric indole-(methyl)thionaphthene-indigos (*loc. cit.*) were found easier to work with in the vat than those of the isomeric (methyl)thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 682 ; 1936, 13, 94 ; 1938, 15, 20 ; 1943, 20, 37). Now it has been found that 3-indole-2'-(5'-chloro)thionaphthene indigos can be worked with in the vat more conveniently than those of the corresponding

isomeric indole(methyl)thionaphthene-indigos. Consequently the shades of these chloro compounds have been quickly and uniformly developed on cotton from alkaline hydro-sulphite vat.

A comparison of colour of these 5'-chloro compounds and their dyeing shades on wool and on cotton with those obtained from their parent compounds, namely, Thioindigo Scarlet R, Ciba Red G and 3(5 : 7-dinitro)indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigo (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 508) and also their 5'-methyl derivatives (Guha and Basu-Mallick, *loc. cit.*) indicated clearly that the effect of a Cl atom in 5'-position of the thionaphthene ring of 3-indole-2'-thionaphthene-indigos is to alter the colour of the parent compounds so that " bathochromic " effect is produced. Secondly, the influence of a Cl atom in 5'-position is more powerful than a methyl radical in the same position in changing the colour of the parent compounds. All these relations will be clearly understood from a comparative study of the dyeing shades obtained from some of the compounds belonging to the three series, described in Table I. The quantitative measurement of the absorption maxima of the 5'-chloro compounds will be communicated later.

TABLE I

Compounds.	Me = Methyl. T = Thionaphthene-indigo	
	Dyeing shade	
	on wool.	on cotton.
3-Indole-2'-T (Thioindigo Scarlet R)	Scarlet-red	Scarlet-red
3-Indole-2'-(5'-Me)T	Brilliant scarlet red	Red (full shade not developed)
3-Indole-2'-(5'-chloro)T	Deep red	Deep red
3-(5 : 7-Dibromo)indole-2'-T (Ciba red G)	Yellowish-red	Yellowish red
3(5 : 7-Dibromo)indole-2'-(5'-Me)T	Deep red	Deep red
3-(5 : 7-Dibromo)indole-2'-(5'-chloro)T	Violet-red	Violet red
3-(5 : 7-Dinitro)indole-2'-T	Dark red	Dark red
3-(5 : 7-Dinitro)indole-2'-(5'-Me)T	Dark red	Dark red
3-(5 : 7-Dinitro)indole-2'-(5'-chloro)T	Violet-red	Deep violet-red

5 : 5'-Dichlorothioindigo(Thioindigo Red BG) was required for another piece of work. It has been described to be a bluish red powder (Rowe, Colour Index, No. 1209, 1924 edition). It has been now obtained in violet-red, well defined crystals from a pure specimen of 5-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Indole-2'-(5'-chloro)-thionaphthene-indigo.—A solution of isatin (0.155 g.) and 5-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.197 g.) in hot glacial acetic acid (43 c.c.) on treatment with concentrated hydrochloric acid (3.5 c.c., *d* 1.12) turned quickly dark red. The whole of the mixture was boiled for 20 minutes during which silky violet-red crystalline dye separated (0.205 g.). It was crystallised from xylene in clusters of star-shaped crystals. It is moderately soluble in xylene and acetic acid; sparingly soluble in benzene and chloroform. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it producing a faint blue colour. It imparts a deep red shade to wool from an acid bath and cotton in the same shade from light greenish yellow hydrosulphite vat. (Found : Cl, 11.44. $C_{16}H_8O_2N$ SCI requires Cl, 11.32 per cent).

3-(5-Bromo)indole-2'-(5'-chloro)thionaphthene-indigo was similarly obtained as violet-red needles from 5-bromoisatin (0.678 g.) and 5-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.553 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (4 c.c.). The dye (0.337 g.) was crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and nitrobenzene (3 : 1) in deep violet-red small needles. It is slightly soluble in chloroform and benzene; insoluble in xylene. The solution in concentrated sulphuric acid is of the same colour as that of the preceding compound. The dyeing shades on wool from an acid bath and on cotton from light greenish yellow hydrosulphite vat are violet-red. (Found : N, 3.73. $C_{16}H_7O_2NClBrS$ requires N, 3.56 per cent).

3-(5 : 7-Dibromo)indole-2'-(5'-chloro)thionaphthene-indigo separated in small thread-like violet-red needles from 5 : 7-dibromoisatin (0.634 g.) and 5-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.384 g.) in 55 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) by heating for 20 to 25 minutes. The product (0.332 g.) was crystallised from pyridine in wooly needle-shaped crystals. It is sparingly soluble in acetic acid and chloroform. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it producing a blue solution. It dyes wool from an acid bath and cotton from light greenish yellow hydrosulphite vat in slightly deeper violet-red shade than that obtained from the 5-bromo dye. (Found : N, 3.35. $C_{16}H_6O_2NClBr_2S$ requires N, 2.96 per cent).

3-(5 : 7-Dinitro)indole-2'-chloro(5'-thionaphthene-indigo was obtained as deep violet-red needles from 5 : 7-dinitro-isatin (0.711 g.) and 5-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.553 g.) in 30 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid (3.5 c.c.) by heating for 20 to 25 minutes. The substance (0.205 g.) was crystallised from benzene in fine, long, pointed needles. It is soluble in acetic acid; moderately soluble in chloroform and benzene. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid producing the same colour as the dibromo dye. It dyes wool in violet-red shade from an acid bath and cotton in deep violet-red shade from yellow hydrosulphite vat. (Found : Cl, 8.3. $C_{16}H_6O_6N_2ClS$ requires Cl, 8.77 per cent).

5 : 5'-Dichlorothioindigo.—5-Chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene, dissolved in hot sodium hydroxide solution (2*N* approx.) was treated with potassium ferrocyanide solution (5%) gradually and shaken. The mixture was heated on the water-bath for 1 hour for the complete precipitation of the dye. The compound separated from nitrobenzene in clusters of needle-shaped violet-red crystals not melting below 305°. (Found : Cl, 19.26. $C_{16}H_6O_2Cl_2S_2$ requires Cl, 19.45 per cent).